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*ЭКСПЕРТ – ЭТО ЧЕЛОВЕК, КОТОРЫЙ
СОВЕРШИЛ ВСЕ ВОЗМОЖНЫЕ ОШИБКИ
В ОЧЕНЬ УЗКОЙ СПЕЦИАЛЬНОСТИ.*

Нильс Бор

Научно-исследовательский институт «Физики резонансных ядерных реакций» является научным учреждением, осуществляющим фундаментальные, прикладные научные исследования и инновационные разработки в области науки, техники, культуры и просвещения.

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QUALITY OF EDUCATION IS AN IMPORTANT FACTOR FOR FURTHER IMPROVEMENT OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF NEW UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: This article reflects the state of the professional education system in New Uzbekistan, existing problems and shortcomings in the organization of distance education, issues of their elimination and training of competitive personnel, trends in the management and development of the quality of education.

Keywords: education, international standards, classifier, distance learning, electronic platforms, scientific potential.

Introduction. In order to ensure the stable and rapid development of the republic's economy, comprehensive, rationally based priority tasks and directions, plans and programs of socio-economic development are being developed for the future. The new market relations being formed in our country and deepening in many aspects are also having an impact on the system of continuing education, including the activities of professional educational institutions, which serve to increase the number and potential of talented, enterprising highly qualified personnel [5].

During the period of modernization and diversification of the economy of Uzbekistan, the tasks of increasing the incomes of citizens, living standards and the volume of gross domestic product produced in the republic, as a result, strengthening the independence of our country, improving the well-being of our people, creating new jobs to ensure employment of the population, improving working conditions, and increasing the intellectual potential of labor resources are also among the urgent issues of today. In the current conditions of globalization and rapid information exchange, the development of any organization, enterprise and institution in accordance with the requirements of the times directly depends on the broad outlook and responsibility of employees, and most importantly, on the knowledge, skills, talents, spirituality, management skills, scientific potential and other characteristics of highly qualified personnel in the leadership and team. Training competitive, highly qualified personnel in professional educational institutions, their targeted use for the peace and prosperity of our country, the well-being of our people is one of the main requirements of a market economy based on strict competition [2].

Research methodology and empirical analysis. In recent years, large-scale work has been carried out in our country to create a professional education system that meets the priority areas of socio-economic development and the requirements of

international standards. In particular, in accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5812 dated September 6, 2019 [1], the activities of vocational colleges in the Republic were terminated and a professional education system was introduced that meets international standards, that is, levels 3, 4, 5 of the UNESCO International Classification of Qualifications (hereinafter referred to as the International Classification or IQC). The establishment of new professional educational institutions in the regions, the opening of modern educational areas and specialties of personnel training, as well as correspondence and evening departments, and an increase in admission quotas to professional educational institutions are important reforms in this direction. In the current conditions, the educational process in vocational educational institutions is carried out on the basis of established educational regulatory documents, and subject curricula are developed in an integrated manner based on the socio-economic development programs of the region and the needs of production sectors. It is natural to ask questions such as: What problems and shortcomings are there in the vocational education system that meets international standards?

In answering these questions, we can explain the problems and solutions as follows. First, in recent years, the spread of infectious diseases that negatively affect human health around the world, including viruses such as coronavirus infection, and preventive measures such as hygiene rules and social distancing among the population have necessitated the transition from traditional forms of education to distance learning in educational institutions. In the higher education system, distance learning has been organized in most higher education institutions based on the MOODLE software learning platform. However, at the same time, due to the lack of “Smart Learning” platforms for implementing the educational process remotely in the professional education system, training sessions have been conducted through social networks and various messengers. This, in turn, has led to problems that negatively affect the continuity of education, such as a decrease in the quality of education, problems in the control system, students' untimely participation in training sessions, problems with the Internet network in the regions, difficulties in using training materials due to their different bit-size, and increased costs for teaching staff and students due to excessive Internet traffic consumption, and as a result, some students did not participate in classes. As an example, it should be noted that in a survey conducted in 2020 on the effectiveness of "online classes" organized due to the pandemic at the Sergali Polytechnic Vocational College alone, only 17 percent of students and their parents expressed a positive opinion, while 83 percent of survey participants thought that the quality of education had decreased.

However, for many years this educational institution has been one of the leading institutions in Tashkent and the Republic in terms of the quality of education

and its rating.

Secondly, the newly established professional education system includes daytime, evening, and correspondence forms of education that are different from the previous vocational education system. Even in the absence of pandemic conditions, the workload of students in correspondence education is significantly different from other forms of education, which leads to a decrease in the quality of education, and students have relatively little knowledge and skills. To eliminate such shortcomings, it is advisable for students in correspondence education to receive education remotely based on a “voluntary lesson schedule”. Thirdly, in accordance with the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Education”, Resolution No. 163 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 29, 2021 was adopted in order to create broad opportunities for young people to support their interest in acquiring professions and specialties and to organize dual education in the professional education system.

In accordance with this resolution, starting from the 2021/2022 academic year, a “dual” education system will be introduced in the vocational education system based on the principle of “lifelong learning”, and learners will be able to strengthen their practical skills in enterprises or production sectors in accordance with their profession and specialization during the remaining working days, and enterprises and organizations will pay learners a salary. Conclusion and discussion. In conclusion, it should be noted that in the current conditions of globalization, training personnel using information technologies plays an important role. After all, we need to widely use information technologies in our daily lives, in the economy, in production and in all areas of our lives. It is the need of the hour that such factors play a leading role in developing the quality of education.

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